

DEFORMATION PATTERN AND FAILURE CRITERIA OF WOVEN COMPOSITE PREFORM IN GENERAL BIAS EXTENSION

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SUMMARY

A series of bias extension tests was carried out on balanced plain woven composite preforms with various aspect ratios, revealing that different aspect ratios may result in different first failures. By competition of the corresponding required energies, the failure of wrinkling or inter-yarn slippage is approximately predicted.

Keywords: Woven composite preform, Bias extension, Wrinkling, Slippage, Energy method

INTRODUCTION

Textile composite materials have demonstrated their superiorities to be structural components due to the physical and mechanical advantages such as high specific stiffness and strength, low weight, nice integral performance, good spatial properties, and so on. In particular, textile composites possess better flexibility than conventional metals so that they can be shaped more easily into many complicated contours. In industry, the most efficient way to form textile composites is through stamping operation [1, 2], in which a flat sheet of material is stamped into a specific shape with a pair of punch and die.

However, a crucial and challenging problem that restricts the stamping operation is the material's formability. Taking a woven fabric textile composite as an example, it is recognized that its primary deformation mode during forming is in-plane large shear deformation between two groups of yarns. In the presence of complex boundary conditions, there are mainly two types of failures: wrinkling [3, 4] and slippage [5, 6]. Inter-yarn slippage, i.e., pulling out of yarns from each other, may occur during shear process, especially when yarns are under tension with free ends. This inter-yarn slippage can be characterized by widely adopted bias extension test [7]. One of the most important and attractive characters of bias extension is that both wrinkling and slippage may possibly take place during the test process. In this connection, a bias extension test involves more complicated factors and information, which is closer to practical deformation cases as occurred in real stamping operations.

Our previous paper [8] has reported an experimental and theoretical study, which includes the analysis of the large deformation behaviour, the determination of the onset of slippage, and the simulation of the load-displacement response of a woven composite preform with an aspect ratio $\lambda = 2$. In the present paper, the bias extension tests with various aspect ratios are described and both wrinkling and slippage failures are investigated. The present study not only aims to characterize the inter-yarn slippage, but also investigates the onset of the two competitive failure modes and their relations under different loading conditions, so as to deepen our understanding on the formability and large deformation pattern of woven composite preforms.

BIAS EXTENSION TESTS

Test Conditions

The test sample was made from continuous E-glass fibers reinforced thermoplastic Polypropylene, as described in paper [8]. Besides $\lambda = 2$ ($230 \times 115 \text{mm}^2$), two other aspect ratios of rectangular specimens were used in the tests: $\lambda = 1.33$ ($230 \times 172.5 \text{mm}^2$), and $\lambda = 1$ ($230 \times 230 \text{mm}^2$). The tension load was applied along the direction 45° inclined to the yarns, by using two steel plates for clamping. The loading speed was 10mm/min , and the loading width was kept as 115mm , smaller than the side length. Tests were implemented with a load cell of 1.5kN on Universal Testing Machine at room temperature.

Test Results

Figure 1. Bias extension test results under 10mm/min at 20°C .

Load vs. crosshead displacement curves under different aspect ratios are plotted in Figure 1. Smaller aspect ratio corresponds to wider specimen that has more material deformed especially at large deformation stage, which results in a larger external load. Comparing the three curves, the force finally decreases in the cases of $\lambda = 2$ and 1.33 ; while for $\lambda = 1$, test was stopped in the middle because the load exceeded the limit of load cell thus no force drop had been observed yet. Another phenomenon is that for $\lambda = 2$, wrinkling is almost invisible throughout the whole test; for $\lambda = 1.33$, wrinkling happened first followed by the inter-yarn slippage; but for $\lambda = 1$, no obvious slippage

was observed until the end of the test while the wrinkling was significant. It indicates that obvious inter-yarn slippage occurs on narrow specimens, and due to larger area of the wider specimens, slippage is harder to take place, which also agrees with our expectation.

Deformation Evolution

Photographs were taken during the tests to trace the deformation process of the material, and digital image correlation analysis was conducted. The calculated maximum shear strain increment fields over the specimen area together with the history of measured shear angle helped to identify a general deformation pattern (see Figure 2), where the top and bottom triangular regions remain undeformed, and the inter-yarn shear angle is γ in the center and $\gamma/2$ in the corner, respectively. The yarn bending effect along the boundaries of relevant regions can be neglected; therefore, different aspect ratios only result in different area of free regions. Particular attentions should be paid that this pattern is only valid within the initial phase of deformation before any failure occurs.

Figure 2. General deformation pattern in bias extension tests.

Together with the photographs, three or four typical deformation phases are identified relevant to densification, failure and post-failure phenomena on the sample, depending on the aspect ratio. For $\lambda = 2$, there are three typical phases (s denotes the crosshead displacement):

- (1) Phase *I* ($0 < s < 45\text{mm}$): 7 regions with different shear angles could be distinguished. Besides shear, additional increasing tension takes place along yarns.
- (2) Phase *II* ($45\text{mm} < s < 70\text{mm}$): Since the yarn tension reaches a critical value and the yarns in the central part are free-ended, they cannot suffer further tension, so that inter-yarn slippage starts from the middle of the sample and extends to both the top and bottom, which can be regarded as the onset of a slippage failure.
- (3) Phase *III* ($s > 70\text{mm}$): Shear deformation ceases and slippage area shrinks as represented by the non-uniformity of the deformation field.

For $\lambda = 1.33$, there exist four typical phases:

- (1) Phase *I* ($0\text{mm} < s < 45\text{mm}$): The same as before except for larger area of the 4 free-end regions around the corners.

- (2) Phase *II* ($45\text{mm} < s < 65\text{mm}$): Since the required energy for inter-yarn slippage is relatively large, wrinkling first occurs instead of slippage.
- (3) Phase *III* ($65\text{mm} < s < 85\text{mm}$): Due to the free end of yarns, slippage happens when the wrinkling gets significant at a larger extension.
- (4) Phase *IV* ($s > 85\text{mm}$): The slippage becomes non-uniform and localized.

The case of $\lambda = 1$ is similar to that of $\lambda = 1.33$, except that slippage happens even later at $s = 75\text{mm}$, and the wrinkling is more serious.

THEORETICAL PREDICTION OF FIRST FAILURE

Test results show that inter-yarn slippage occurs for $\lambda = 2$, but in the cases of $\lambda = 1.33$ and 1, wrinkling first occurs instead of the slippage. The theoretical prediction of initial failure with different aspect ratios is of great interest to explain the experimental observation, to regulate the forming conditions and to improve the formability. An energy method was adopted to predict the load-displacement response for $\lambda = 2$ [8], and it is applicable for any other aspect ratios. In the following, the energy method, whose feasibility has been verified in Refs [8, 9], is used again to determine the initial failure in the tests with three different aspect ratios.

There are three possible deformation modes which dominate bias extensions: in-plane shear, out-of-plane wrinkling, and inter-yarn slippage. Different mechanisms can be reflected by their corresponding parts of energy during the fabric's deformation, so the material's behaviour has three possible bifurcations, and the real one renders the minimum consumed energy. In view of this basic consideration, the energy increments of the three modes should be estimated, respectively.

First, we consider the case of $\lambda = 2$. According to the proposed deformation pattern, by neglecting the influence of additional yarn tension, the in-plane shear energy increment over the whole specimen is equal to

$$dW_s = d\bar{W}_s(\gamma) \cdot A_{center} + d\bar{W}_s(\gamma/2) \cdot A_{corner} \quad (1)$$

where $d\bar{W}_s(\gamma)$ is the shear energy increment per area obtained from the experimental result of the picture frame test [10]; A_{center} and A_{corner} are the areas of central and marginal parts, respectively. Since the central shear deformation is larger than the corner one, if wrinkling happens, it will first locate merely in the central region, thus the wrinkling energy increment is equal to

$$dW_{wrinkle} = d\bar{W}_{wrinkle}(\gamma) \cdot A_{center} / 4 \quad (2)$$

where $d\bar{W}_{wrinkle}(\gamma)$ is the wrinkling energy increment in a fabric element [9]. To estimate the energy dissipated by inter-yarn slippage, it is assumed that although observed slippage always localizes in local regions, every fabric element which has the

tendency to slip should reach the same critical state exactly before slippage happens. Therefore, the energy increment dissipated by slipping is found to be

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} dW_f(\gamma) = \sum \mu \cdot A \cdot [\bar{P}(\gamma) + \bar{N}(\gamma)] \cdot d\Delta \\ \bar{N}(\gamma) = 2\mu \cdot \sum 2\bar{P}(\gamma) \cdot \frac{2t_0}{w_0} + \bar{N}_0 \\ d\Delta = 2w_0(\cos[(90^\circ - \gamma - d\gamma)/2] - \cos[(90^\circ - \gamma)/2]) / \cos[(90^\circ - \gamma)/2] \end{array} \right. \quad (3)$$

where $\bar{P}(\gamma)$ is the transversely compressive force to yarns per area [8]; $\bar{N}(\gamma)$ is the normally compressive force per over-lapping region; $\bar{N}_0 = 0.05N$ is the measured initial normally compressive force in a unit cell; $d\Delta$ is the relative sliding displacement; $\mu = 0.35$ is the sliding frictional coefficient between yarns; Σ represents the summation of the corresponding effective areas, which will be generally discussed in next Section; w_0 and t_0 are initial yarn width and thickness, respectively.

By applying Equations (1), (2), (3), and canceling $d\gamma$ for all cases, the nominal energy increments of the three deformation modes over the whole specimen are represented by the central shear angle as shown in Figure 3. It reveals that before central shear angle reaches 41° , where the displacement is about 40mm, in-plane shear has the minimum energy increasing rate, which agrees with the real deformation in this stage; later on, the curve of slippage first intersects with the shear one, indicating that inter-yarn slippage will take place at this point, which is also in a good accordance with the experimental observation (displacement $s = 45\text{mm}$).

Figure 3. Nominal energy increments of three possible deformation modes for $\lambda = 2$.

As for $\lambda = 1.33$ and 1, the estimations of shear and slipping energy increments remain the same, except that relevant effective area increases with smaller λ , i.e., wider specimen. A main difference rests with the wrinkling energy. Since the loading width (115mm) at two sides is smaller than the width of the specimen (172.5mm for $\lambda = 1.33$ and 230mm for $\lambda = 1$), localized horizontal compressive stress will be induced in the

central region; as a result, the central region gets additional inward compression, which accelerates the onset of wrinkling. However, it is difficult to analytically obtain the internal compression due to the large deformation state and non-uniform fabric structure. In this regard, a simple equivalent force analysis in a macroscopic scale is utilized based on the textile structure. As sketched in Figure 4, the test process is regarded to be quasi-static, so every part of the specimen should keep equilibrium under external forces. As the left-side triangular part **A** is under tensions T along the two groups of crossing yarns directly from **B** and **C**, there must be another outward force F' to keep it in balance. Contrarily, the central region receives the reactionary inward force, F' , that accelerates wrinkling.

Figure 4. Equivalent inward compressive force to the central region.

For simplicity, an approximate assumption is made that the external tension $F/\sqrt{2}$ is equal to the addition of all the static friction in parts **A**, **B**, **D**, and the friction is distributed uniformly with respect to area. Consequently, after subtracting the frictions in **B** and **D**, the remained tension to part **A** is

$$T = \frac{0.3 \cdot F}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (4)$$

where F is the total external force obtained from the experiment as a function of shear angle γ . Accordingly, the resultant inward compressive force to the central region is

$$F' = 0.3 \cdot F \cdot \sin(\pi/4 - \gamma/2) \quad (5)$$

By employing the formula for the wrinkling energy increment [9], where F' does negative work, the energy increment in a fabric element is found as

$$d\bar{W}_{wrinkle} = \frac{8EI \cdot \cos \gamma \cdot d\gamma}{D} + 2w_0 \left[\mu\bar{N} \left(1 + \frac{3\gamma}{2\pi}\right) \sqrt{\frac{\cos \gamma}{\pi}} + 2\bar{P} \sin \gamma + 2\mu\bar{P} \cos \gamma \right] \cdot d\gamma \quad (6)$$

$$-0.3F \cdot \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{\gamma}{2}\right) \cdot w_0 \cos \gamma \cdot d\gamma$$

where $EI = 2.4 \times 10^{-7} \text{ Nm}^2$, $D \approx 17.5 \mu\text{m}$, $w_0 = 4.34 \text{ mm}$, $\mu = 0.3$, $\bar{N} = 0.05 \text{ N}$. On the other hand, because the compressive force F' only locates near the left vertex of the central region, and if the effect is supposed to decrease linearly from the left vertex to zero at the top vertex, the average of the force should be roughly halved with respect to the whole central region. Finally, the wrinkling energy increment of the whole specimen should be

$$dW_{wrinkle} = 66 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot d\bar{W}_{wrinkle} \quad (7)$$

where 66 is number of fabric elements in the central region.

Based on the formulae given above, the nominal energy increments in the cases of $\lambda = 1.33$ and $\lambda = 1$ are plotted in Figure 5 and Figure 6, respectively. Comparing the energy increments of three possible deformation modes, it is clearly seen that wrinkling happens when the central shear angle reaches about 43° for $\lambda = 1.33$ and 41° for $\lambda = 1$. In the account of larger internal compression induced in the wider specimen, the required wrinkling energy is less than that in narrower one; consequently, the local wrinkling in wider specimen happens earlier. Referring the relationship between shear angle and displacement, our theoretical analysis predicts the critical displacement at wrinkling as 45mm for $\lambda = 1.33$ and 43mm for $\lambda = 1$, respectively, which agrees well with the experimental results. Throughout the whole test process, the curve of slipping energy is always not the minimal one, which interprets that slippage will not occur. However, the deformation pattern of the specimen, as well as each deformation mode, may greatly change after wrinkling, so the curves are no longer reliable. In this regard, the theoretical model can only be used to determine the onset of initial failure, while the material's post-failure behaviour is not our concern and indeed it is less important in the practical forming process.

Figure 5. Nominal energy increments of three possible deformation modes for $\lambda = 1.33$.

Figure 6. Nominal energy increments of three possible deformation modes for $\lambda = 1$.

GENERAL CRITERION OF FAILURE IN BIAS EXTENSION

Previous analysis has shown that the area of free-end and central regions is crucial to the failures, and whether slippage and wrinkling occurs or not depend on the relative magnitude of corresponding energies consumed. To express the energy increments as functions of the aspect ratio and loading width, a general case is considered, where the tensile loading width is H_0 , sample width is W_0 ($W_0 \geq H_0$), and sample length is L_0 ($L_0 > H_0$), otherwise two ends of yarns will be clamped in the fixture with no deformability), the required energy increment can be estimated by the map shown in Figure 7.

The potential shear energy involves all the areas except the top and bottom undeformed triangles, where the shear angle is γ in the central region, and is $\gamma/2$ in all other regions. The wrinkling energy is estimated merely in the central region, taking into consideration of the localized inward compression as discussed above. To estimate the slipping energy, yarns are classified into two types: those represented in dashed line are completely free-ended, which can slide both parallel to each other and with respect to the crossing ones; in other words, both \bar{P} and \bar{N} should be incorporated in the sliding friction; on the other hand, yarns in solid line are half free-ended, which can only slide with respect to the crossing groups, only with \bar{N} being considered. Based on these idealizations,

corresponding effective areas of each deformation mode in different regions can be estimated, and the energy increments can be derived as functions of geometrical dimensions, H_0 , W_0 , L_0 , and γ , with given material properties. Detailed expressions are skipped here to save space. General conclusions are that wide specimen with smaller aspect ratio benefits wrinkling and toughens inter-yarn slippage, and larger loading ratio makes wrinkling easier to happen rather than slippage.

Figure 7. Deformation map of a general bias extension test.

CONCLUSIONS

Bias extension tests were conducted on the specimen of balanced plain woven textile composite preforms with different aspect ratios. For various aspect ratios and loading ratios, different first failure modes were observed from experiments. Large deformation process was analyzed with a general pattern proposed, where three or four typical phases can be identified. There are three possible deformation modes throughout the test, i.e., in-plane shear, out-of-plane wrinkling and inter-yarn slippage. Shear deformation and yarn tension pre-dominate the initial phase, and slippage or wrinkling happens afterwards beyond the limit of static friction and in-plane shear, respectively. In the post-failure phase, the deformation field becomes non-uniform, leading to a separation of specimen in a localized region. To build a theoretical model, the energy method has been utilized again to reveal the relative possibility of each deformation mode. From the theoretical results, the onset of first failure mode with different aspect ratios is predicted, demonstrating good agreement with the experiment. It is concluded that small loading ratio to the specimen causes localized inward compressive stress which spurs wrinkling, and that large area of free-ended region prevents early slippage. The significance of this study recommends a uniform loading condition in the forming of woven textile composite preforms during stamping, as well as fixed ends of yarns or larger area of free-ended regions if possible.

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